

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with Acetothioacetanilide

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Iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) have been extracted into chloroform from solutions of pH 7.1-8.3, 8.4-11.9 and 6.8-8.3 respectively as acetothioacetanilide complexes. The absorbance values of the extracts were measured at 500 nm, 625 nm and 496 nm respectively against pure chloroform and the metals have been determined with relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.19\%$, $\pm 1.15\%$ and $\pm 1.47\%$ in the same order. The effect of the presence of various foreign ions have been studied and a procedure for the estimation of nickel content of steel has been developed.

ACETOACETANILIDE has been found to be a very selective reagent for beryllium^{1,2} and similar metals with 'hard acid' properties as defined by Pearson³. Harries and Wright⁴ as well as Kettrup and Riepe⁵ have studied the properties of such complexes. Das and co-workers have used several other reagents having coordination sites similar to acetoacetanilide to improve upon the methods of estimation of beryllium⁶⁻⁸ and other metals of 'hard acid' type.

In this investigation, acetothioacetanilide, $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, a new reagent coordinating through the carboxyl and thiocarboxyl groups instead of two carboxyl groups as in the compounds mentioned above has been introduced with the expectation of being selective for metals bordering between 'hard' and 'soft' acid type metals. Iron(III), cobalt(III) and nickel(II) have been observed to form chelates with this reagent with metal to reagent ratios 1:3, 1:3 and 1:2 respectively⁹. Methods for the spectrophotometric estimation of these three metals have been described here.

Experimental

Acetothioacetanilide solution: The reagent was prepared in the laboratory following the method due to Barnikow, Kunzek and Richter¹⁰. Thiodiacetoacetylaniide was first prepared from acetylacetone and phenyl isothiocyanate which on hydrolysis produced acetothioacetanilide. Finally this was crystallised from 40% aqueous ethanol.

The pale yellow crystals of acetothioacetanilide melting at 63°-64° were soluble in all common organic solvents. The solubility of the reagent in water of pH around 7.0 was appreciable. Acetothioacetanilide is a mild reducing agent and its dissociation constant was determined by Bjerrum titration. The pka value was found to be 3.09×10^{-9} . The reagent decomposed slowly after 2-3 months unless preserved in a dark and cool place, preferably in a refrigerator.

Three sets of the ethanolic solution of the reagent of concentrations, 5% (0.26M), 7.5% (0.39M) and 11% (0.57M) were used.

Iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) solutions: Ferric chloride (G.R., E.Merck), cobalt sulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) and nickel chloride (G.R., E.Merck) were dissolved separately in dilute acid, estimated following conventional methods¹¹⁻¹³ and suitably diluted to obtain final concentrations of 50, 200 and 250 μg per ml of iron, cobalt and nickel respectively.

All the reagents used were of A.R. or G.R. grade

Apparatus: The optical measurements were carried out in a Hilger and Watts H 700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched glass cuvettes. A battery-operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used for the adjustment of pH.

Extraction procedures:

Iron(III): A known amount (1-7 ml) of the stock iron solution was taken in a 50 ml separatory funnel, diluted to 15 ml and 1 ml of acetothioacetanilide (11%) solution was added. The pH was adjusted to 7.1-8.3 with 1.0M ammonium hydroxide. The complex formed was extracted with 10 ml chloroform. The extract was transferred to a 10 ml measuring flask and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance was measured at 500 nm using pure chloroform as blank.

Cobalt(II): An aliquot (1-10 ml) of the stock cobalt solution was taken in a 50 ml separatory funnel and 1 ml of the reagent (7.5%) solution was added. The mixture was diluted to 20 ml with water and the pH was adjusted above 8.4 by drop-wise addition of 2M ammonium hydroxide and was shaken for 2-3 min. The complex was extracted with 10 ml of chloroform and transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask.

Traces of water present were removed with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance was measured after 20 hr at 625 nm against pure solvent.

Nickel(II): A desired quantity (1–6 ml) of the nickel solution was mixed with 1 ml of the reagent (5%) solution in a 50 ml separatory funnel and diluted to 10–15 ml. The pH was raised to 6.9 or above by the careful addition of an aqueous solution of triethanolamine (20%). After shaking for 5 min. the complex was extracted with 10 ml of chloroform. The extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance was measured at 496 nm against pure solvent within 1–2 hr after the extraction.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: For the determination of iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) in the presence of diverse ions the appropriate procedure was followed. In the presence of manganese (II), 0.25 g of ammonium bifluoride was required in case of iron. For the determination of cobalt or nickel in presence of iron(III), either 2 ml of triethanolamine or 0.25 g of sulphosalicylic acid was used as the masking agent.

Procedure for the determination of nickel in steel: Each of the samples of steel was decomposed with 1:1 hydrochloric-nitric acid mixture and heated to fumes with sulphuric acid. After dilution with water, the solution was filtered and the filtrate was made to 250 ml in a measuring flask.

A suitable aliquot (5 ml) of the solution was taken in a 50 ml separatory funnel, diluted with water to 10 ml and 1 g of sodium-potassium tartrate dissolved in 5 ml of water was added followed by the addition of 1 ml of ethanolic acetothioacetanilide (1%) solution. The pH was raised to about 7.0 with triethanolamine (20%) solution and the mixture was shaken for 3 min. Then 10 ml of chloroform was added and shaken again for 5 min. The addition of 1 g of ammonium bifluoride dissolved in minimum volume of water at this stage followed by 1 min of shaking hastened the separation of the layers. The non-aqueous layer was separated, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance was measured at 496 nm. The results of the determination of nickel content of several samples of steel have been given in Table I.

TABLE I.—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN STEEL

Sample	Ni found (%)	Rel. Error (%)
C, 0.39%; Mn, 0.79%	1.14	-0.87
Ni, 1.15%; Cr, 0.69%	1.145	-0.43
C, 0.1%; Cr, 17.51%	9.49	+0.35
Ni, 9.48%	9.45	-0.32
C, 0.06%; Cr, 16.47%	13.65	+1.64
Ni, 16.47%; Mo, 2.7%	13.61	+1.34

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves: The absorbance values of the iron-, cobalt- and nickel- complexes in the range

400–750 nm were recorded after extracting different quantities of the metals in chloroform. Reference solutions were prepared by treating 10 ml of the reagent (5%, 7.5% or 11%) solution in the same way. Each of the metal complexes showed two peaks: iron 420, nm. 500 nm; cobalt around 430 nm, 625 nm and nickel 400–405 nm and 495–500 nm. In each case the peak at lower wave-length was more sharp. However, the wave-lengths 500 nm (for

Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of iron(III)-, cobalt(II)- and nickel(II)- acetothioacetanilide complexes.

- (a) Fe(III)-complex (11.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CHCl_3);
- (b) Ni(II)-complex (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CHCl_3);
- (c) Co(II)-complex (105 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CHCl_3);
- (d) Reagent (11%) blank.

iron), 625 nm (for cobalt) and 496 nm (for nickel) were selected as the reagent had no absorption above 480 nm. Thus pure chloroform could be used as reference. Representative curves for one concentration for each species have been presented in Figure 1.

Selection of the extracting solvent: Chloroform, isobutylmethyl ketone, *n*- and iso-amylalcohol and tributylphosphate extracted all the complexes. However, the cobalt complex was decomposed within 5 hr after extraction when any solvent other than chloroform was used. Chloroform was selected due to its lower cost and ease in purification, operation and recovery.

Effect of pH: The effect of pH on the extraction was studied by extracting the same quantity of the metal concerned at different pH-values and measuring the absorbance of the extracts. The aqueous layers left after extraction were also subjected to proper qualitative tests. The results confirmed that the pH ranges for quantitative extraction were: 7.1–8.3 for iron(III), 8.4–11.9 for cobalt(II) and 6.8–7.0 for nickel(II). In case of nickel, complete extraction was possible upto pH 8.3, but the stability of the colour was reduced. The use of ammonia instead

of triethanolamine also reduced the stability in this case.

Effect of the concentration of the reagent : From experiments using 20–120 mg of the reagent it was concluded that the minimum quantities of it required for each extraction were : 100 mg for iron, 50 mg for cobalt and 40 mg for nickel provided the complexes were allowed to form in the aqueous layer before extraction.

Effect of number of extraction : The measurement of the absorbance of two successive extracts in each case showed that for all these three metal complexes, one extraction was sufficient for the quantitative transfer into the chloroform layer.

Stability of colour : The absorbance of the iron-acetothioacetanilide complex remained unchanged for 2½ hr while that of the cobalt complex was stable upto 20 days after extraction. In case of the nickel-complex the duration was 5 hr when the extraction was carried out at pH 6.8–7.0, but it was only 2 hr if the pH was 8.3.

Conformity to Beer's Law : When the absorbance values were plotted against concentration, straight lines were obtained for 4–35 µg of iron, 20–200 µg of cobalt and upto 150 µg of nickel per 1 ml chloroform.

Effect of sequestering agents : The presence of tartrate, fluoride, sulphosalicylic acid or triethanolamine did not interfere with the determination of cobalt or nickel. However, nickel formed an emerald green complex¹⁴ with triethanolamine but its stability was lower than that of the complex with acetothioacetanilide, thus it did not interfere with the extraction. The presence of fluoride helped quick separation of layers. The presence of ethylenediaminetetraacetate, citrate, thioglycolic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid interfered with the extraction of nickel and cobalt. Iron(III) could not be determined in the presence of any one of the above mentioned substances.

Tolerance limit for diverse ions : Iron(III) (119 µg) could be estimated in the presence of 0.05 mg of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺, Mn²⁺, MoO₄²⁺ or WO₄²⁻ or 1.00 mg of AsO₄³⁻. For cobalt(II) (750 µg) 10.00 mg each of Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sb³⁺, AsO₄³⁻, 1.00 mg of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺, Sn²⁺ and over 30 mg of Mg²⁺ or MoO₄²⁻ showed no interference. In the presence of sulphosalicylic acid upto 10 mg of Fe³⁺ could be tolerated. However, the presence of ammonium biftuoride was necessary to mask Mn²⁺. Nickel(II) (1 mg) could be determined in the presence of double the quantity

of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺, Sn²⁺, AsO₄³⁻, MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻ or 0.2 mg of Cr³⁺. When triethanolamine or sulphosalicylic acid was used as the masking agent 100 mg of Fe³⁺ did not interfere. The maximum amount of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺ or Ba²⁺ which could be present was 0.05 mg.

Optimum concentration range and sensitivity : The optimum concentration ranges were 4–14 µg of iron(III), 22–70 µg of cobalt(II) and 30–105 µg of nickel(II) per millilitre of chloroform. Sandell sensitivity¹⁵ for iron was 0.02 µg per cm², for cobalt 1.0 µg per cm² and for nickel 0.15 µg per cm².

Molar absorptivity and standard deviation : The molar absorptivities were found as : iron 2763 (500 nm), cobalt 589.3 (625 nm) and nickel 396.3 (496 nm), while the relative standard deviations were ±0.19%, ±1.15% and ±1.47% respectively for iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II).

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